

Supplementary Figure 1 – Coverage of segmental duplications (duplicons) with repeat elements (transposable elements, W-Elements and tandem repeats). Window for each respective duplicon extended 2,000bp upstream and downstream. Red dashed line indicates the genomic mean for the respective repetitive element.